

**SPRAY DEPOSITION PROCESSING OF
Al/SiC/GRAPHITE HYBRID METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES
FOR INTRINSIC DAMPING**

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ABSTRACT

The present paper reports on the results of a systematic study of the damping behavior of Al/SiC/graphite hybrid metal matrix composites, processed by spray atomization and co-deposition. Spray atomization and co-deposition was utilized in the present study because of its ability to incorporate non-metallic particulates into a metallic phase under relatively low processing temperatures, thereby avoiding interfacial reactions. The selection of SiC particulates was prompted by its ability to increase the stiffness and strength of Al, whereas the graphite particulates were selected for their attractive damping characteristics. The results of the present work show that it is possible to synthesize Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMCs using spray atomization and co-deposition without degradation of the graphite particulates. Furthermore, the results of damping characterization studies show that the value of the logarithmic decrement, δ , of the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC is 2 - 4 times higher than that corresponding to unreinforced and reinforced 6061 materials. The relatively high damping characteristics of the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC obtained in the present work were attributed to the presence of the graphite and SiC particulates, although the precise damping mechanism remains to be established.

Key Words: Metal Matrix Composites, Damping, Aluminum, Graphite Particulates, Silicon Carbide Particulates, Spray Deposition Processing, Solidification.

1. INTRODUCTION

The less than optimum damping response of frequently utilized metals and alloys has prompted investigators to explore the possibility of improving the damping characteristics of structural materials through modifications to the microstructure and/or through innovative processing. With the advent of metal matrix composites (MMCs) technology it became possible to modify the physical and mechanical properties of metals and alloys by combining them with non-metallic phases.^[1-10] Ceramic reinforced metals, for example, combine metallic properties of ductility, toughness and environmental resistance with reinforcement properties of high strength and high modulus.^[3, 4, 9] The behavior of MMCs is largely dictated by the characteristics of the metal/ceramic interface. As a result, the metal/ceramic combinations that are readily attainable with currently available processing technology are constrained by the relative thermodynamic compatibility of the combined phases, as well as by the thermal conditions present during processing.^[7-11] For example, incorporation of graphite particulates into aluminum, at elevated temperatures such as those that are present during casting, may result in extensive formation of carbide phases, with concomitant degradation in mechanical properties.^[9-11] In view of these limitations, and in an effort to expand the range of possible metal/ceramic combinations, there are extensive research efforts aimed towards the development of novel synthesis techniques for MMCs.^[9, 12-14]

Recently, spray atomization and deposition processes have received considerable attention for the synthesis of discontinuously reinforced MMCs as a result of a number of factors.^[15-22] First, because of highly efficient heat convection during atomization, relatively low processing temperatures can be maintained, and hence, deleterious interfacial reactions can be minimized. This provides the opportunity to process metal/ceramic combinations that would otherwise react extensively when exposed to elevated temperatures. Second, spray atomized and deposited materials have been reported to exhibit some of the characteristics associated with rapid solidification, namely: fine grained microstructures, increased solid solubilities, non-equilibrium phases and the absence of macro-segregation. Third, spray atomization and co-deposition processes have the potential of being utilized for near net shape manufacturing of difficult to form materials, such as intermetallics (e.g., Ni₃Al). Spray atomization and co-deposition processing involves the mixing of the reinforcements and the matrix in a regime of the phase diagram where the matrix contains both solid and liquid phases. In principle, such an approach will inherently avoid the extreme thermal excursions, with concomitant degradation in interfacial properties and extensive macrosegregation, normally associated with casting processes. Furthermore, this approach also eliminates the need to handle fine reactive particulates, as is necessary with powder metallurgical processes.

This work reports on a study of the damping behavior of spray atomized and deposited Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMCs. The selection of SiC particulates was prompted by its ability to

increase the stiffness and strength of a metallic matrix, whereas the graphite particulates were selected for their attractive damping characteristics. 6061Al alloy was chosen as the matrix material, first, because its damping behavior has been studied extensively, and second, because this type of alloy has been widely used in structural applications.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material Synthesis The 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC was synthesized in an environmental chamber using spray atomization and co-deposition processing (Figure 1). The matrix material used in the present study was a commercial quality 6061 aluminum alloy, with the following nominal composition: 0.6% Si, 0.28% Cu, 1.0% Mg, 0.2% Cr, and balance Al (in wt. %). The reinforcing and damping particulates were Phase α -600 single crystal SiC powders and Phase 2935 crystalline flake graphite powders, respectively. The characteristics of these two types of particulates are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Materials Used in Study.

<u>Material</u>	<u>Aluminum</u>	<u>SiC</u>	<u>Graphite</u>
Type	6061	α -600	2935
Supplier	Commercial	Exolon Co.	Superior Graphite Co.
Density	2.730 g/cm ³	3.100 g/cm ³	2.025 g/cm ³
Mean Particle Size	-----	15 μ m	5 μ m

Spray atomization and deposition processing involves the energetic disintegration of the molten 6061 alloy into micron-sized droplets by high velocity inert gas jets (N₂ was used in the present study). As the atomized metallic droplets travel towards a deposition surface, two jets of ceramic particulates are simultaneously co-injected into the atomized spray at a previously determined flight distance. The precise co-injection position is determined on the basis of numerical analysis of the fraction solid and the temperature of the atomized matrix droplets, as a function of flight distance; a more thorough discussion of the numerical analysis results is available elsewhere.^[9, 15, 17] In the present study, equal volumes of the SiC and graphite particulates were mixed in a "V" blender, placed inside a fluidized bed chamber, and co-injected into the atomized droplets using an inert gas; a more thorough discussion of the injection procedure is available elsewhere.^[15] The mixture of rapidly quenched, partially solidified droplets with interdispersed ceramic particulates impacts, first, on the deposition surface and, subsequently on each other, and collect as a preform the microstructure of which is largely dictated by the solidification conditions during impact. The primary processing variables used during the experiment are listed in Table 2.

The geometry of the spray deposited material, which normally exhibits a contour akin to the Gaussian distribution of droplets impacting on the substrate^[23-27], was readily modified in the

present study by displacing the substrate during deposition. In order to avoid extensive oxidation of the 6061 Al matrix during processing, the environmental chamber was evacuated to a pressure of 0.02 Pa, and backfilled with N₂ gas to a pressure of 0.1 MPa prior to melting and atomizing the material. A more detailed discussion of the spray atomization and deposition experiments may be found elsewhere.[15, 23-28]

Table 2. Processing Variables Used in the Study.

Atomization Pressure	1.14 MPa
Atomization Gas	Nitrogen
Flight Distance	40.64 cm
Pouring Temperature	800 °C
Metal/Gas Mass Flow Rates	2.29
Injector Distance to Atomizer	25.4 cm
Injection Angle	90°
Injector Pressure	0.31 MPa

Figure 1. Schematic diagram showing spray atomization and co-deposition processing.

2.2 Macrostructural Characterization

The geometry of the spray atomized and deposited material is shown schematically in Figure 2. The approximate dimensions of the as-spray deposited material were as follows: Width = 18 cm, Length= 38 cm, and Height = 7 cm. In Figure 2, the orientation of the Z axis was selected to lie in the thickness dimension, whereas the orientation of the X and Y axes were chosen to lie in the short transverse and long transverse directions, respectively.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram showing morphology of as-spray deposited 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC.

Cantilever beam specimens for damping characterization and samples for microstructural analysis were simultaneously removed by sectioning the as-spray deposited material into rectangular bars. The following procedure was adopted in order to keep track of the precise location of each sample within the spray deposited material. The central core of the deposit was first sectioned into a block with the following approximate dimensions: 15 cm long \times 7.5 cm wide \times 7 cm high. This block was subsequently sectioned into rectangular samples as shown in Figure 3. In this figure, the relative location of each rectangular specimen inside the spray deposited block is designated by a number. Every rectangular sample was subsequently divided into two parts; one was used for the damping specimens, and the other for volume fraction and porosity analyses (see Figure 4). This procedure allowed careful analysis of the microstructure present in the damping specimens, since the microstructure of spray atomized and deposited materials has been reported to change with spray deposited thickness (Z axis), but remains relatively constant along the long transverse dimension (Y axis).^[29, 30]

Figure 3. Schematic diagram showing position of samples within the as-spray deposited material.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram showing specimen configuration and geometry.

2.3 Microstructural Characterization Optical microscopy was conducted on polished and etched (Keller's reagent) as-deposited samples using conventional and Differential Interference Contrast (DIC) techniques; the use of DIC microscopy facilitated identification of the SiC and graphite particulates in the matrix. In order to provide an accurate value of the volume fraction of secondary particulates present in the spray deposited samples, two methodologies were used in the present study: chemical dissolution and image analysis. The chemical method involved measuring the mass of composite samples, dissolving the samples in a solution of 36% hydrochloric acid (HCl), followed by filtering to separate the SiC and graphite particulates. The SiC particulates were separated from the graphite particulates by oxidizing the filtrate material at a temperature of 800 °C, in order to remove the graphite. The mass changes were carefully recorded during the entire procedure, and the mass of each constituent was determined accordingly. It is worth noting that a series of control experiments were conducted in order to insure that the HCl did not react with the SiC and graphite particulates during dissolution of the matrix. The volume fraction corresponding to each of the constituents was determined from the following equations

$$V_{SiC} = M_{SiC} / \rho_{SiC} \quad (1)$$

$$V_{Gr} = M_{Gr} / \rho_{Gr} \quad (2)$$

$$V_{Al} = (M - M_{SiC} - M_{Gr}) / \rho_{Al} \quad (3)$$

$$P = 1 - V_{Al} - V_{SiC} - V_{Gr} \quad (4)$$

where V, M, ρ and P denote volume fraction, mass, density and porosity, respectively; the subscripts SiC, Gr, and Al refer to the silicon carbide, graphite and aluminum, respectively.

Computerized image analysis was used to confirm the results from the chemical dissolution experiments. In addition, the distribution of particulates and pores present in the microstructure was quantitatively characterized using computer aided image analysis. The image analysis was conducted on a Macintosh IIfx computer and a Nikon Epiphot optical microscope. An adaptor was utilized in the present work to transmit images from the optical

microscope directly to the computer, where the size distribution was readily established. This procedure allowed the efficient characterization of a large number of metallographic samples.

2.4 Damping Measurements The cantilever beam technique was used in the present study to characterize the microstructural damping response of the spray deposited materials. In this technique, one end of a rectangular specimen was fixed in place while the opposite end was allowed to respond freely to a mechanically induced displacement or vibration. The damping capacity of the material was then determined from the resulting displacement spectrum, by utilizing the logarithmic decrement and the half power band width analysis methodologies. In the logarithmic decrement method, a history of amplitude versus time during a free vibration of the cantilever beam specimen was recorded. By measuring the amplitude decay, the logarithmic decrement, δ , can be determined by the following equation

$$\delta = (1/n) \ln (A_i / A_{i+n}) \quad (5)$$

where A_i and A_{i+n} are the amplitudes of the i^{th} cycle and the $(i+n)^{\text{th}}$ cycle, at times t_1 and t_2 , respectively, separated by n periods of oscillation.

The half power band width methodology is based on a forced vibration test. In this technique the resonant frequency peak is distinguished by recording the vibration amplitude as a function of frequency. The damping loss factor, Q^{-1} , may then be calculated from the vibration spectrum using the following equation

$$Q^{-1} = (f_1 - f_2) / f_r \quad (6)$$

where f_r , f_1 , and f_2 are the resonant frequency, and frequencies at half power band width, respectively. Finally, the relationship between the logarithmic decrement, δ , and the loss factor, Q^{-1} , was determined from the following equation

$$Q^{-1} = \delta / \pi \quad (7)$$

All of the damping data used in the present study was derived from experiments performed at the Westinghouse Science and Technology Center (Pittsburgh, PA).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Volume Fraction The results of the volume fraction studies, using acid dissolution and image analysis, are summarized in Table 3. In this table, V_T , represents the total volume fraction of particulates present in the matrix, obtained by adding the respective volume fractions of the SiC, V_{SiC} , and the graphite, $V_{Gr.}$, as determined by chemical dissolution (Eq. 1 - 3). The overall amount of porosity present, P , was also determined from the acid dissolution studies (see Eq. 4). The last column in Table 3, V_{Total} , represents the overall volume fraction of SiC, graphite, and pores present in the microstructure, and was determined using computer aided image analysis. Comparison of the results obtained from the summation of V_T and P to V_{Total} shows good agreement between the chemical dissolution and image analysis techniques, although the results from the chemical dissolution studies are considered more accurate.

Table 3. Volume Fraction Results Obtained Using Image Analysis and Acid Dissolution.

¹ Sample	² V _{SiC} (%)	² V _{Gr.} (%)	³ V _T (%)	² P (%)	⁴ V _{Total}
622	2.75	2.63	5.38	5.92	12.23
623	3.39	3.28	6.67	5.91	17.33
624	3.60	3.70	7.30	6.37	13.18
625	3.62	3.98	7.60	6.75	13.55
643	5.07	4.48	9.55	7.80	15.10
644	5.43	4.77	10.2	8.87	16.22

¹See Figure 3, ²Determined by acid dissolution, ³V_T = V_{SiC} + V_{Gr.}, ⁴Determined by image analysis.

3.2 Microstructure Optical microscopy was conducted on coupons of the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite materials; one example is shown in Figure 5. This figure reveals the presence of an equiaxed grain morphology, with an average grain size of 10 μm . This grain morphology, which is characteristic of spray atomized and deposited materials, has also been reported by other investigators.[23-29] The average grain size for all of the samples studied was in the 8 - 20 μm range, depending primarily on the location of the sample within the spray deposited material. Similar grain sizes have been reported by other investigators for spray atomized and deposited 6061 Al.[33, 36] Inspection of Figure 5 shows that while a proportion of the particulates penetrated the atomized droplets, some of them may be seen decorating prior sput boundaries; this is an area of further study. In addition, the results from image analysis studies showed that the average particulate size was approximately 6 μm , which compares favorably with the dimensions of the graphite particulates, as shown in Table 1.

Figure 5. Optical micrographs showing a) the microstructure, and b) the distribution of particulates in the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC.

3.3 Damping Capacity The damping response of the spray deposited composite materials, as determined from the experimental data in combination with Equations (5) and (6), are summarized in Table 4. Also shown in this table is the Lorentzian peak frequencies, f_r , for each of the samples tested. It is worth noting that the free decay vibration tests were performed at a frequency of 220 Hz. Comparison of the values of the logarithmic decrement, δ , to those of the loss factor, Q^{-1} , using Eq. (7) suggests good agreement between the logarithmic decrement and the half power band width analysis methodologies. It is important to note, however, that the difference between the two frequencies in the half power band width methodology was generally small, decreasing the accuracy of the computed loss factor, Q^{-1} (see Eq. 6). Therefore, the logarithmic decrement, δ , was deemed as a more accurate measure of the damping behavior of the spray deposited materials, and will be used hereafter in the discussion.

Table 4. Damping Capacity of As-Spray Deposited 6061 Al/SiC/graphite Hybrid MMC

Sample	δ (%)	f_r (Hz)	Q^{-1} (%)
622	3.0	287.50	0.6
623	1.9	-----	-----
624	2.2	295.00	0.8
625	2.8	296.75	0.7
643	1.8	295.75	0.7
644	2.3	-----	0.7

¹See Figure 3.

4. DISCUSSION

The microstructural damping capacity of a material - referred to hereafter simply as damping capacity - may be defined as its ability to dissipate elastic strain energy, although plasticity may be involved at large strain amplitudes. The dissipation of elastic strain energy in the microstructure typically occurs through a combination of several mechanisms, which include: 1) relaxation of point defects, 2) macro-thermoelasticity, 3) micro-thermoelasticity, 4) Eddy-current effects 5) Snoek effect, 6) stress-induced ordering reactions, and 7) electronic effects^[31]. In addition, the dissipation of elastic strain energy may be affected by discontinuities that may be present in the microstructure, such as grain boundaries, cavities, and interfaces.^[31-35] The relative contribution of each of these mechanisms to the overall damping response of the material depends, not only on their volume fraction, but also on their natural oscillatory frequency.^[36]

The damping capacity of the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC obtained in the present study is summarized in Table 5, where the value of the logarithmic decrement, δ , is compared to the results obtained by other investigators using alloys of equivalent composition. The value of the

logarithmic decrement, δ , shown in Table 5 was the average of the six samples investigated (see Table 4). The results show that the value of δ of the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC is 2 - 4 times higher than that corresponding to unreinforced and reinforced 6061 materials. The higher damping capacity of the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC, relative to that of the unreinforced 6061 Al alloy may be understood by considering the damping capacity of each of the components constituting the MMC, since any damping mechanisms that may be active in the Al matrix will be present in the reinforced and unreinforced materials. The results obtained in the present study show, that in addition to the SiC and graphite particulates, there was a distribution of micron-sized pores present in the microstructure (see Table 3). The effects of these pores, which result from the arrival of partially solidified droplets on the deposition substrate^[15, 27], on the damping capacity are not clearly understood. However, there is experimental evidence recently available suggesting that the presence of porosity may enhance the intrinsic damping response of spray deposited materials.^[37] Regarding the contribution of the SiC to the overall damping response of the MMC, the work of Wong and Holcomb^[38] on SiC and Al₂O₃ reinforced Al alloys suggests that these types of reinforcements may have an important effect on the damping behavior of the MMCs. Furthermore, the work of Updike et al.^[39] shows that the presence of graphite fibers enhances the damping behavior of the MMCs, particularly when there are no interfacial reactions at the Al/graphite interface. The relatively high damping capacity of graphite has been rationalized in terms of the importance of shear deformation mechanisms in the bulk mechanical behavior of graphite, and the presence of a high density of glissile dislocations.^[35] Furthermore, the work of Baghat et al.^[40- 42] and Rawal et al.^[43] shows that the loss factor of graphite fiber reinforced MMCs increases with the volume fraction of graphite fibers, and that the damping level of the composites far exceeds the damping level of the matrix aluminum and the carbon fiber. In view of these results, the relatively high damping characteristics of the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC obtained in the present work may be attributed to the presence of the graphite and SiC particulates, although the precise mechanism remains to be established. There are other microstructural factors that may influence the damping capacity of the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC; these include: metal/ceramic interfaces, reaction products, fine grained microstructure and porosity. Further work is continuing in this area in order to ascertain the mechanisms that are responsible for the observed damping behavior.

Table 5. Comparison of Damping Capacity of 6061 Al Based Materials.

Material	Ref.	V _f (%)	Test	Freq.	δ (%)
6061/SiC/Gr	Present Work	7.8 Total 3.8 Gr.	Cantilever beam	220 Hz	2.33
[± 60] _s P55Gr/ 6061 MMC	[36]	46	Cantilever	20 Hz	1.36
6061-T6	[42]	----	Cantilever	500 Hz	0.62
6061-T651	[36]	----	Cantilever	19.8 Hz	0.65

5. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the results of the present work show that it is possible to synthesize Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMCs using spray atomization and co-deposition without degradation of the graphite particulates. Furthermore, the results of damping characterization studies show that the value of δ of the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC is 2 - 4 times higher than that corresponding to unreinforced and reinforced 6061 materials. The relatively high damping characteristics of the 6061 Al/SiC/graphite hybrid MMC obtained in the present work were attributed to the presence of the graphite and SiC particulates, although the precise damping mechanism remains to be established. Further work is continuing in this area in order to ascertain the mechanisms that are responsible for the observed damping behavior.

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